

A Method for the Measurement of Digitizers' Absolute Phase Error

G. Crotti¹, A. Delle Femine², D. Gallo², D. Giordano¹, C. Landi², M. Luiso², A. Scaldarella²

¹Istituto Nazionale di Ricerca Metrologica (INRIM), Torino, Italy

²Dept. of Engineering, University of Campania "Luigi Vanvitelli", Aversa (CE), Italy

E-mail: mario.luiso@unicampania.it

Abstract. A lot of engineering applications, from telecommunications to power systems, require accurate measurement of phase angles. Some of them, like synchrophasor measurement and calibration of instrument transformers with digital output, in order to reach high phase measurement accuracy, require the knowledge of phase error of digitizers. Therefore, in this paper a method for the measurement of digitizers' absolute phase errors is proposed. It adopts a sinewave and two square waves, that are the digitizer sample clock and a phase reference signal. Combining the measurements of the relative phase differences between the adopted signals it is possible to accurately evaluate the absolute phase error of a digitizer.

1. Introduction

The knowledge of phase angles of signals is at the base of many engineering applications, from telecommunications to power systems ([1]-[5]). In particular, in most measurement applications, electronic instrumentation is based on digitizers, to convert analog signals to digital samples, and digital signal processors, to get the desired measurement value. However, every digitizer has its own phase frequency response which introduces a phase deviation between the analog input and its digital output samples. In some applications this phase deviation can be considered negligible, with respect to the measurand, and in others one could be interested only in the phase delay of two channels of the same digitizers, such as in energy or power measurement. Generally speaking, measuring the relative phase delay between two different channels of the same digitizer, or two channels of two different digitizers that have synchronized sampling clocks, is an issue solved in a number of scientific papers ([6]-[8]). However, there are special applications, such as Phasor Measurement Unit (PMU) ([9], [10]) or calibration of Low Power Instrument Transformers (LPIT) ([11]-[13]) with digital output (having as a reference an instrument transformer with analog output), where high phase accuracies, sometimes in the order of microradians, are required. In these situations, the absolute phase deviation of the single channel of the used digitizer may be comparable or higher than the required accuracy, introducing an unacceptable systematic error that highly influences the measurement result. An interesting technique for measurement of digitizer absolute phase error is proposed in [14], that involves the generation of a reference signal with known phase with respect to a time reference. In this paper, a technique for measuring the absolute phase errors of digitizer is presented. It is based on the preliminary characterization of the phase error of the used signal generator, through the use of a phase comparator ([6]-[7]). By means of a frequency counter, which measures the time delay between the sampling clock

The digitizer used for the phase comparator is, instead, the module NI PXI 4462 (+/- 10 V, 24 bit, maximum sampling rate of 204.8 kHz). Excluding the comparator, which operates asynchronously, all the instruments of the test bench use clocks generated by the NI PXI-6683H synchronization board, so they are all synchronous. In particular, the sampling frequency of the AWG is 5 MHz, while the sampling clock of the DUT is 1 MHz. The PRS is generated by the NI PXI-6683H, too. A digital storage oscilloscope (Tektronix TDS 2014B) is used to control the correct operation of the setup. The block diagram of the measurement setup is shown in Fig. 2, where C_{DUT} is the DUT sampling clock and C_{AWG} is the sampling clock of the AWG.

The sine wave is connected to both the DUT and the COMP. The COMP measures the phase difference between the sine wave and the PRS. The frequency counter receives a 10 MHz clock as external timebase and measures the time delay between PRS and DUT sampling clock.

All the clock and signal paths are symmetric in order to avoid different propagation delays. Since the two input channels of COMP and of the counter could have inter-channel time (or phase) delay, in order to compensate for these systematic errors, two measurements are performed, interchanging the signals between the two channels, both for COMP and counter ([1]).

Measurement software is developed in LabVIEW. For each test point, amplitude and frequency of the test signal of the DUT can be chosen and 30 repeated measurements of $\angle F[S_{DUT}(kT_s)]|_{f_0}$, τ_c and $\varphi_g(f_0)$ are performed.

An automated test, sweeping frequency of the test signal from 50 Hz to 20 kHz, has been performed. Two amplitudes, 5 V and 10 V, and a constant DUT sampling frequency of 1 MHz have been chosen.

Fig. 3 shows the DUT phase frequency responses, at 5 V and 10 V, where, for each point, mean value and standard deviation is plotted.

It is worth noting that the DUT does not use antialiasing filter. Therefore, as expected, its phase error is linearly dependent on the input signal frequency and it is due to an almost constant time delay introduced by the digitizer in its bandwidth.

Fig. 2. Measurement setup.

Figure 3. DUT phase frequency response.

4. Conclusion

In this paper a new technique for the measurement of digitizers' absolute phase error is presented. A commercial digitizer has been characterized changing input signal characteristics, i.e. amplitude and frequency. However, the technique is general and can be applied to evaluate the absolute phase error of every digitizer.

References

- [1] G. Aurilio, M. Balato, G. Graditi, C. Landi, M. Luiso, M. Vitelli, "Fast Hybrid MPPT Technique for Photovoltaic Applications: Numerical and Experimental Validation," *Advances in Power Electronics*, vol. 2014, Article ID 125918, 15 pages, 2014. doi:10.1155/2014/125918, June 2014
- [2] D. Gallo, R. Langella, M. Luiso, A. Testa and N. R. Watson, "A New Test Procedure to Measure Power Electronic Devices' Frequency Coupling Admittance," in *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*.
- [3] G. Crotti, D. Giordano, M. Luiso and P. Pescetto, "Improvement of Agilent 3458A Performances in Wideband Complex Transfer Function Measurement," in *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 66, no. 6, pp. 1108-1116, June 2017.
- [4] G. Crotti, D. Gallo, D. Giordano, C. Landi and M. Luiso, "A Characterized Method for the Real-Time Compensation of Power System Measurement Transducers," in *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 64, no. 6, pp. 1398-1404, June 2015.
- [5] G. Crotti, D. Gallo, D. Giordano, C. Landi, M. Luiso, "FPGA-based real time compensation method for medium voltage transducers", *ACTA IMEKO*, vol. Vol 4, p. 82-89, ISSN: 2221-870X, Year 2015
- [6] B. Trinchera, D. Serazio, and U. Pogliano, "Asynchronous phase comparator for characterization of devices for pmus calibrator", *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, 66(6):1139–1145, June 2017.
- [7] G. Crotti, D. Gallo, D. Giordano, C. Landi, and M. Luiso, "Industrial comparator for smart grid sensor calibration", *IEEE Sensors Journal*, 17(23):7784–7793, Dec 2017.
- [8] E. Mohns, J. Meisner, G. Roeissle, and M. Seckelmann, "A wideband current transformer bridge", *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, 63(10):2322–2329, Oct 2014.
- [9] P. Tosato, D. Macii, M. Luiso, D. Brunelli, D. Gallo and C. Landi, "A Tuned Lightweight Estimation Algorithm for Low-Cost Phasor Measurement Units," in *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 67, no. 5, pp. 1047-1057, May 2018.
- [10] D. Gallo, C. Landi, M. Luiso, P. Tosato, D. Macii, D. Brunelli, "A Testbed for the Experimental Characterization of Estimation Algorithms for Phasor Measurement Units" 2017 IEEE International Workshop on Applied Measurements for Power Systems (AMPS), Liverpool, United Kingdom, 2017, pp. 118-123.
- [11] G. Crotti, D. Gallo, D. Giordano, C. Landi, M. Luiso, "Medium Voltage Divider Coupled With an Analog Optical Transmission System", *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 63, p. 2349-2357, October 2014
- [12] G. Crotti; D. Gallo; D. Giordano; C. Landi; M. Luiso; M. Modarres; M. Zucca, "Frequency Compliance of MV Voltage Sensors for Smart Grid Application," *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 17, no. 23, pp. 7621-7629, Dec.1, 1 2017. doi: 10.1109/JSEN.2017.2726116
- [13] G. Crotti; D. Gallo; D. Giordano; C. Landi; M. Luiso; M. Modarres, "Frequency Response of MV Voltage Transformer Under Actual Waveforms", *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 66, no. 6, pp. 1146-1154, June 2017, ISSN: 0018-9456, DOI: 10.1109/TIM.2017.2652638
- [14] M. Acanski, G. Rietveld, and D. Hoogenboom, "Accurate phase calibration of pmus and pmu calibrators", In 2016 Conference on Precision Electromagnetic Measurements (CPEM 2016), pages 1–2, July 2016.